

IMPACT OF PARENTING STYLE AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract:

The difficult period of adolescence is when the basis for the best possible development of a person's personality is set. Adolescents undergo significant mental, physical, and psychological changes as they grow and develop, and these changes are profoundly influenced by their familial environment in numerous and long-lasting ways. Parents' parenting practises and emotional intelligence are revealed to be crucial factors in adolescents' academic success. Therefore, the current study's main focus is on how parental practises and emotional intelligence affect teenagers' academic accomplishment.

Keywords: *Parenting Style, Academic Achievement, Adolescents, Family Environment, Behaviour etc.*

Introduction

Adolescence is a crucial and transformative time for adolescents, during which time they must deal with a variety of challenges connected to their social, academic, and achievement lives. In India, there is a lot of pressure to achieve well in school, especially for young people enrolled in pre-university courses because their grades would determine their future careers and level of success. Academic success is characterised by how well pupils do in the subjects they are taught in school. Teenagers who perform well in school are thought to be liked by their classmates, teachers, and parents; they are recognised in society; they have better employment options; they become more capable of taking on leadership roles; and they acquire greater self-confidence and self-esteem. Academic failure, however, leads to dissatisfaction, stress, inferiority complex, rejection, increased suicide rates, dropping out of school or college, greater rates of unemployment, and antisocial conduct. (**Pandey, 2016**).

Individual characteristics like cognitive ability, self-concept, and sense of control, school characteristics like teacher expectations, and family characteristics like parenting styles, financial position, and cultural differences are some of the elements linked to academic accomplishment. Many psychosocial and demographic factors combine to shape academic achievement. Although many factors—both cognitive and non-cognitive—play a significant role in academic achievement, the roles of two non-cognitive factors—parenting practises and emotional intelligence—are of particular interest because of the significant social and cultural transition known as globalization—which is happening in India as a result of technological, ecological, legal, and cultural changes. (**M. S. Gore, 2013**).

Conceptual Framework

It is essential to conceptualize and operationally define the concepts and terms related to the present field of study. The key concepts included for this purpose are adolescence, parenting styles, emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

Parenting Style

Mother and father are responsible for parenting as a method of child rearing, either jointly or separately, in order to prepare the child for society and culture and provide them the chance to establish roots, maintain continuity, and feel a sense of belonging. To raise children who are emotionally, academically, and socially competently is the aim of parenting. As a result, parents play crucial responsibilities in overseeing, directing, and initiating their children's chances and social interactions. (**Buriel, 2015**).

The typical methods parents employ to raise their children are referred to as parenting style. According to **Baumrind (1966)**, these styles are divided into three categories based on the degree to which parents exercise control over and demonstrate warmth towards their children's behaviours. These styles are

based on two dimensions: control and warmth. These are authoritative, authoritarian and permissive styles.

In authoritarian style of parenting, parents attempt to shape, control and assess behaviour and attitudes of their children according to certain absolute set of standards, emphasize obedience, respect for authority and maintenance of order.

In authoritative style, parents show an expectation of mature behaviour from the child. Parents very clearly set standards, enforce rules firmly, use commands and sanctions when necessary, encourage the child's independence and individuality.

A third pattern is permissive parenting style where parents accept and tolerate child's impulses, use little punishment, make few demands for mature behaviour, allow for considerable self-regulation by the child. While lacking in control, parents often excel at being friendly and receptive. A lack of impulse control, lack of self-reliance, immaturity, lack of independence, lack of social responsibility, and poor academic performance were the results of this parenting style in pre-schoolers.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence (EI) has been conceptualized in two distinct ways, one as a set of abilities for processing information and secondly as a set of personality traits. The concept of emotional intelligence was first introduced by *Salovey & Mayer (1990)* who connected emotions to intelligence and saw emotional intelligence as more of ability than personality. Later, more comprehensive theories developed by other theorists, who connected academic performance to a variety of non-cognitive skills and abilities that affect one's capacity to handle life's demands and pressures. The utility or suitability of the method used to examine emotional intelligence is still up for debate because studies validating ability and personality measurements are still in their early stages.

There may be variations in emotional intelligence due to demographic characteristics like gender, financial background, and family structure. Studies have revealed that men and women have varied emotional IQs because of how society socialises the two genders differently. Females in India are historically raised to fit into the wider society's requirements, and understanding, accepting, and adjusting is a significant cultural value that helps females develop stronger interpersonal skills. Because boys are biologically able to control their emotions and express themselves in ways that are socially acceptable, boys endure less worry and emotional turmoil than girls do in India's primarily patriarchal society. Since schools and colleges now offer equal possibilities for self-awareness and self-expression activities, their emotional intelligence can be improved as a result of globalisation. According to *Chu (2012)*, men exhibit higher levels of emotional intelligence than women. According to *Dunn (2012)*, girls scored higher than boys in the areas of empathy, social responsibility, and interpersonal relationships. In their interactions with their parents, friends, and siblings, they shown greater sensitivity. In Chandigarh teenage populations, *Katyal and Awasthi (2006)* discovered strong associations between emotional intelligence and the kind of household, parents' educational attainment, and mother's occupation, as well as higher emotional intelligence in females than males. The monthly income, birth order, or father's career did not significantly affect emotional intelligence, nevertheless.

Academic Achievement

Academic achievement is defined as "knowledge attaining ability or degree of competence in school tasks usually measured by standardised tests and expressed in a grade or units based on pupils' performance", specified level of proficiency in scholastic or academic work, and the extent to which a learner is gaining knowledge from instruction in a particular subject.

Academic success is seen as a predictor of future success and an indicator of learning, but it is also influenced by a variety of factors, including self-assurance, competence, emotional stability, individual ability, motivation, parenting styles, parental support, socialisation, early instruction and experience, and parental and educator expectations (*Wentzel, 2014*).

Methodology

The paper is based on secondary research regarding the parenting style and academic achievement concept conducted on previously published articles, journals, research papers, newspapers, magazines, and the internet. Analysis is done based on such research, and the conclusion is presented in the form of a paper.

Parenting Style and Academic Achievement

Parental support of their children's academic pursuits is crucial for greater academic performance. School achievement was correlated with verbal interaction between mothers and their offspring, parental expectations of offspring's academic performance, parental views and attributions about offspring, good emotional connections between parents and offspring, and control and punishment techniques. Discipline and control techniques are among those that have a significant impact on academic performance.

According to some studies, authoritative parenting practises are strongly linked to individualistic cultures and are therefore responsible for adolescents' greater academic success. In contrast, other studies show that authoritarian parenting practises are strongly linked to collectivist cultures and are therefore responsible for adolescents' greater academic success. India is in a state of transition due to cultural blending, altered family structures, and the impact of globalisation. The impact is on the parents and their style of upbringing children. Although individualistic and collectivistic cultures have different effects on parenting styles, there may be a general societal tendency towards a more tolerant and democratic form of parenting that needs to be investigated as a result of globalisation and the mixing of cultures (*Gore, 2013*).

Authoritative parenting style as the most successful style for developing academically and socially competent children. Children flourish academically in these kinds of environments. According to these studies, it can be observed in teenagers of all ages and across all socioeconomic categories (*Simons & Conger, 2017*).

Authoritative parenting style has a positive influence on self-regulated learning. Asian parents performed well on tests of their level of authoritarian parenting, which is linked favourably to their children's academic success. Similar findings were found in studies utilising Indian samples (*Uredi, 2018*). Parents' encouragement of boys and girls differently, according to gender, is another example. Girls are taught to develop attachment inclinations, whereas boys are pushed to acquire competitive and achievement-oriented traits. Parents are likely to reward their sons for good behaviour and they anticipate their sons to perform well in school.

Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement

Adolescents who are better able to control their emotions can cope with daily challenges, which helps with psychological adjustment and, in turn, with adjustment to academic demands. Today, emotional intelligence rather than only cognitive ability is thought to be the key to an individual's success. Academic success depends on how one handles daily obstacles, the anxiety associated with failing, and the pressure to succeed. A high level of emotional maturity will be necessary to handle these difficulties. Several psychological processes have an impact on academic success. Academic success may be influenced by emotional intelligence as well as parenting style. Higher academic success requires strong emotional intelligence and self-management skills. *Esiobu (2011)* advocates using cooperative learning as an intervention technique to help students understand one another and develop tolerance, teamwork, and conflict resolution skills. Students who have a greater grasp of their own emotional states, as well as those of others, can exercise their interpersonal and intrapersonal abilities more effectively. Therefore, having a positive outlook about oneself can help one perform better in school. Enhancing physical and mental abilities can lead to a strong academic record, personal fulfilment, and job achievement. Emotional intelligence plays a significant role in this process.

Academic competence requires persistence, concentration, and maintaining one's attention on the task at hand. They will be able to exercise Meta cognitive control on both an intrapersonal and interpersonal level with the aid of emotional intelligence abilities, and they will be able to independently monitor and manage their learning. They will learn more easily and with greater motivation. Problem-based learning and cooperative or collaborative learning both call on the interpersonal skills component of emotional intelligence (*Evans, 2016*). Adolescents that have strong emotional intelligence find it

simple to participate in collaborative or cooperative learning or peer supported learning. Their social skills, empathy, ability to provide constructive criticism, and encouragement will all be developed and improved as a result. For minority kids who live in urban areas with low incomes, it is highly successful in raising achievement, social competence, self-concept, and task behaviour.

Parenting Style and Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence was found to be positively correlated with perceived home and school environmental quality by *Rai and Pandey in 2019*. From an Indian perspective, emotional intelligence is context-dependent, and a person's family plays a significant part in influencing their emotional development. Parents place a strong emphasis on relational socialisation, which is defined in terms of relatedness and interdependence. Male Khasi adolescents from India's North East suffered more rejection than female counterparts, although female Mizo adolescents received more rejection than male counterparts. However, Khasi females perceived fathers' emotional warmth better than men did, and there was no difference for the mother. Khasi society is matrilineal, which may be the cause of the pupils' rejection. According to *Cheng (2011)*, mothers who exert reasonable amounts of discipline with their kids are better able to boost their self-esteem.

The development of emotional intelligence is influenced differently by each parenting style. An authoritarian parent will not approve of the teenager's feelings, may criticise, be judgmental about their emotions, consider expressing emotions to be a sign of weakness, and may even punish the adolescent for doing so while defending it as their way of showing love and concern. The value of emotional intimacy is not taught to their children as adolescents by such parents. They begin to believe that expression of emotions leads to abandonment, humiliation, pain and abuse (*Agochiya, 2015*). A permissive parent provides consolation but does not advise their child on how to deal with their feelings. These kids also have trouble controlling their emotions.

One's emotional life may be affected negatively by the harshness, kindness, or empathetic understanding of parents. Children learn through the way their parents interact with them how to feel and respond to their own feelings, how others will react to them, what choices they will make in response to those options, and how to express their hopes and anxieties. In addition to what parents say and do directly to their children, parents also set an example for how to manage their own emotions and those of their partners. This is how this emotional education works.

Conclusion

The study result shows that how parenting style and emotional intelligence affected academic achievement. Adolescents initially experience, observe, and learn about emotional relationships in their families. Parenting requires the ability to protect children from the hazards they may encounter and to guide them in the right direction. Adolescents attempt to comprehend their feelings through parental modelling and bonding. Our first place to learn about emotions is in the family. Even so, a mother's parenting style and interactions with her adolescent have a greater influence on their social and emotional growth. The psychological environment of the family has a significant impact on how emotionally intelligent the child is. In families with strong warm feelings among their members, emotional awareness and management are most robust. Strong family ties are frequently associated with the ability to manage other people's emotions, while individuals who believe their own family life to be "natural" are the least likely to be able to do so. The results also indicated that the students' academic success is impacted by the parents' authoritarian parenting style.

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